

Quantifying Green IT: Architectural Complexity and Runtime Power Dynamics for Web Frameworks

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Abstract

The energy footprint of software is an increasingly critical factor in green computing, yet the role of web framework architecture remains under explored. Building on the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS) and previous ADRN-2 findings, this study provides a cross-language analysis of eight web frameworks across PHP, Ruby, Python, and JavaScript. Using Intel RAPL telemetry on a hardware-normalized dual-server setup, this study isolates the architectural complexity contribution of each framework.

By introducing Software Median Power Overhead (SMPO) and Software Complexity Power Jitter (SCPJ), this research demonstrates that minimalist frameworks maintain near-baseline energy consumption with high stability, whereas full-featured frameworks impose architectural penalties and intermittent power spikes. These results confirm that software design is a primary determinant of energy efficiency. Future work should extend this analysis to include memory usage and caching mechanisms to provide a holistic assessment of the environmental impact of software complexity.

Introduction

The environmental impact of computing has become a critical concern, as software-driven energy consumption often negates the efficiency gains achieved by modern hardware. While previous energy efficiency research has largely focused on programming languages or algorithmic optimization, the role of software architectural complexity in the web context remains under-explored.

This study builds upon the findings established in Audax Development Research Notes 1 and 2. The first introduced the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS), demonstrating a clear correlation between a PHP framework's structural overhead, quantified by the count of classes, interfaces, traits, and functions, and its consumption of system resources like memory and execution time. The second extended this investigation by correlating the ACS of six popular PHP frameworks (Laravel, Symfony, Laminas, CodeIgniter 4, Yii, and Fat-Free) directly with physical electrical draw measured via Intel Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) telemetry. That work concluded with the Davanzo Corollary to Wirth's Law:

"Software increases its energy demand more rapidly than hardware improves its power efficiency."

The current research expands this scope to a multi-language spectrum, comparing web development frameworks across PHP, Ruby, Python, and JavaScript. I examine a range from micro-frameworks, such as Fat-Free Framework (F3), Sinatra, Flask, and Fastify, to heavyweight enterprise stacks like Laravel, Ruby on Rails, Django, and Express.js.

While the ACS metric was originally validated for PHP, this study operates on the hypothesis that the architectural delta between a micro-framework and its full-featured relative is a universal driver of energy demand.

Literature Review Recap

Current discourse on software sustainability is divided between the inherent efficiency of programming runtimes and the practical implementation of architectural patterns. Research by Pereira et al. (2017, 2021) established a ranking of programming languages based on energy consumption, positioning compiled languages like C as the gold standard, while interpreted languages like PHP, Python, and Ruby occupy the higher end of the energy spectrum. This work provided a vital baseline for understanding the inherent efficiency of various runtimes.

However, Mytton (2022) challenged the finality of these rankings, arguing that the most efficient language "depends" on the specific context, workload, and implementation. The ADRN-1 (Davanzo, 2025) bridges these perspectives by introducing the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS) and identifies the framework architecture as the primary driver of the "it depends" variable. The ADRN-2 (Davanzo, 2026) extended this to physical electrical draw via Intel Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) telemetry, proving that complex architectures force a higher power usage.

Methodology

As in ADRN-2, the experiment was conducted using a dual-server setup in order to ensure that the energy consumed by the Test Runner does not interfere with the energy measurements of the Web Server. Two Dell Optiplex 3040 units, named Edsger and Niklaus, connected via TP-Link LS1005G 5-Port Gigabit Ethernet Switch have been used (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 1: Test network setup

Figure 2: Test servers

Both servers are equipped with CPU Intel Core i3-6100T @3.20GHz, 12GB RAM and 128GB SSD with Alpine Linux v3.23, The latter is a lightweight distribution built on the musl C library and BusyBox utilities. This permits to obtain a reduced system footprint which minimizes noise in the RAPL readings.

All frameworks under test were installed following their official documentation and recommended configuration guidelines to ensure consistency and reproducibility. Furthermore, each framework was configured to operate in production mode to accurately reflect realistic deployment conditions. This decision is crucial, as modern web frameworks often enable performance optimizations exclusively in production environments, including various forms of caching, precompilation, and runtime optimizations.

Basic hello world template

Full-stack web frameworks typically activate multiple architectural subsystems even when processing trivial requests. These commonly include routing layers, configuration loaders, dependency injection containers, helper registries, lifecycle hooks, and view abstraction mechanisms. While such components enable developer productivity and extensibility, they introduce execution overhead that is independent of the functional requirements of the request itself. Micro-frameworks, by contrast, are intentionally designed to minimize abstraction layers and internal orchestration. Their execution paths are generally shorter, requiring fewer object allocations, reduced dependency resolution, and less runtime coordination to produce equivalent responses. This architectural divergence is central to energy analysis. Even when two frameworks generate identical outputs, the internal computational work performed by the runtime may differ significantly due solely to framework design.

For this reason, the study adopts a deliberately minimal workload: a single-route endpoint rendering a static HTML template with one variable, `greeting`, assigned the value "hello world". Under these conditions, variability introduced by application logic is effectively eliminated, allowing energy measurements to primarily reflect framework-induced accidental complexity rather than functional computation. The template used across frameworks is structurally similar to the code below.

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
  <title>Test Page</title>
</head>
<body>
  <p><%= greeting %></p>
</body>
</html>
```

The test-framework.sh script

Consistent with the need for environmental isolation, the test script begins by normalizing the remote server's hardware state via SSH.

It executes `performance.sh` and `noturbo.sh` already used on ADRN-2, to lock clock speeds and disable Intel Turbo Boost, ensuring that power fluctuations are the result of software complexity rather than dynamic hardware scaling.

The test suite iterates through a list of micro-frameworks and enterprise stacks (F3, Laravel, Sinatra, Rails, Flask, Django, Fastify, and Express). Each framework undergoes a multi-stage lifecycle to capture the Cold Start and Operational energy profiles:

- The framework is started using its native production runner (e.g., `php-fpm` for PHP, `Puma` for Ruby, `Gunicorn` for Python, or `PM2` for Node.js). A 10-second `START_SLEEP` allows the service to initialize before logging begins.
- The `raplog.sh` utility (RAPL reader) is launched on the remote server to capture energy draw.
- The script sends a `curl` request for a specific url with a configurable interval and duration in seconds.
- To prevent the affecting of subsequent tests, a 30-second cooldown period follows the termination of each service.

The methodology relies on the synchronization of two distinct log streams:

- *Event Log* (`<testname>_events.csv`): A local CSV tracking every `curl` request, timestamped to the nanosecond, including the HTTP status code.

- *Power Log* (<testname>_rapl.csv): A remote CSV capturing the electrical draw from the CPU's Model Specific Registers (MSR) via the RAPL interface.

Startup & Teardown Strategy

Because each framework employs a different runtime model and process management mechanism, lifecycle control cannot be uniform. Table 1 summarizes the operational characteristics of each framework, highlighting whether it relies on system-managed services, application-level servers, or a hybrid model.

Framework	Runtime Model	Notes
F3 (Fat-Free Framework) 3.9.2-Release	PHP-FPM + Nginx	Relies on system services
Laravel	PHP-FPM + Nginx	Requires correct working directory
Sinatra	Puma (Ruby)	Application-level server
Rails	Puma (Ruby)	Similar model to Sinatra
Flask	Gunicorn + Nginx	Hybrid service/application model
Django	Gunicorn + Nginx	WSGI application server
Fastify	Node.js (PM2) + Nginx	Process manager abstraction
Express	Node.js (PM2) + Nginx	Similar lifecycle to Fastify

Table 1: Runtime model of each framework

Below the list of each framework and service version used for the test.

Service version	Framework version
PHP 8.5.2 (cli) (built: Jan 20 2026 19:04:03) (NTS) ruby 3.4.8 (2025-12-17 revision 995b59f666) +PRISM [x86_64-linux-musl] Python 3.12.12 Node v24.13.0 nginx version: nginx/1.28.0 gunicorn 24.0.0 PM2 6.0.14 Puma 7.2.0	Fat-free: 3.9.2-Release Laravel: 12.48.1 Rails: 8.1.2 Django: 6.0.1 Flask: 3.1.2 fastify: 5.7.2 Express.js: "5.2.1"

Table 2: Framework and service version

Results

It is critical to analyse these results without dismissing small numerical differences. In a global data centre context, a constant delta of 0.01W or 0.05W per server scales linearly across thousands of nodes and millions of execution hours. What appears as a small decimal in a single-instance benchmark translates into Kilowatts of wasted energy at scale.

The 20-second window - 1 request every 0.01s

The 20-second window is a critical value for identifying the high-intensity energy transients associated with framework bootstrapping. The primary justification for the 20-second test is the observation of the initialization spike, most notably in the Ruby on Rails framework (Figure 8).

Figure 3 F3

Figure 4 Laravel

Figure 5 Flask

Figure 6 Django

Figure 7 Sinatra

Figure 8 Ruby on Rails

Figure 9 Fastify

Figure 10 Express.js

When analysing framework power draw, the use of averages are misleading because they are sensitive to the initialization spikes mentioned. A single high-intensity transient (like the Ruby on Rails boot sequence) can artificially inflate a mean value, masking the framework's actual steady-state efficiency. The use of the median allows us to isolate the typical operational power draw, effectively filtering out the noise of framework bootstrapping and garbage collection spikes.

The data confirms that minimalist architectures consume less power. Sinatra and Fat-Free establish the lower bounds of the energy spectrum with Medians of 3.815267W and 4.021627W, respectively. When comparing within the same language runtime, the impact of architectural choice become evident:

- PHP: Moving from F3 to Laravel results in a 24.5% increase in median power draw.
- Ruby: Moving from Sinatra to Rails increases the median draw by approximately 6%, but the real cost is hidden in the initialization peak already discussed.
- Python: Moving from Flask to Django results in around 0.7% increase in median power draw.

- Javascript: the data reveals a counter-intuitive trend regarding Fastify. Marketed as a highly performant and low-overhead framework (The Fastify team, no date), Fastify actually exhibits a 1.63% higher median power draw than Express.

TAG	COUNT	MIN	AVG	MEDIAN	MAX
F3	54	2.454217	3.958854	4.021627	4.456287
Laravel	54	2.441767	4.942299	5.005725	6.176314
Sinatra	54	2.459772	3.742579	3.815267	4.167470
Ruby on Rails	54	2.432428	4.796350	4.057546	10.082066
Flask	54	2.428521	4.037330	4.085103	4.613575
Django	54	2.451044	4.057585	4.110341	4.707203
Fastify	54	2.457514	4.257985	4.319509	4.709827
Express.js	54	2.478509	4.169440	4.250295	4.659718

Table 3: Summary of the 20-second window test with 1 request every 0.01s

The 120-second window - 1 request every 0.01s

While the extended window amortizes initialization transients, the median remains the most reliable indicator of continuous architectural overhead, as it is robust against framework's maintenance processes. The mean is reported as a complementary measure reflecting the cumulative influence of periodic runtime activity.

Figure 13: Sinatra

Figure 14: Ruby on Rails

Figure 15: Flask

Figure 16: Python

Figure 17: Fastify

Figure 18: Express.js

By examining the median power draw, the impact of architectural choice remains visible but shifted toward the framework's continuous overhead:

- PHP: The architectural penalty remains the most severe in the PHP ecosystem. Moving from F3 to Laravel results in a 24.06% increase in median power draw. This confirms that Laravel's overhead is not merely a startup cost but a permanent architectural complexity paid during every request cycle.

- Ruby: With the initialization spike diluted, the delta between Sinatra and Rails settles at 3.50%. This probably represents the steady-state cost of Rails' larger internal dependency graph compared to Sinatra's minimalist approach.
- Python: In this high-intensity window, the delta between Flask and Django remains the narrowest of all ecosystems at 1.34%. This suggests that the Python interpreter itself is likely the dominant energy consumer, regardless of whether a micro or full-stack framework is utilized.
- JavaScript: The performance-centric Fastify continues to show a slightly higher baseline than Express, with a 1.64% higher median power draw. This confirms the results of the 20-second window.

TAG	COUNT	MIN	AVG	MEDIAN	MAX
F3	321	2.467340	4.038174	4.050222	4.347401
Laravel	321	2.465814	5.018474	5.024707	6.397994
Sinatra	321	2.428583	3.802318	3.835927	4.105764
Ruby on Rails	321	2.432062	4.080650	3.970144	10.103002
Flask	321	2.432488	4.088757	4.105764	4.460865
Django	321	2.442620	4.150786	4.160634	4.559681
Fastify	318	2.471063	4.296894	4.309865	4.718250
Express.js	320	2.479913	4.233312	4.240407	4.596973

Table 4: Summary of the 120-second window test with 1 request every 0.01s

The 120-second window - 1 request every 2.00s

This dataset, representing a low-load scenario (1 request every 2 seconds), reveals the quiescent power draw inherent to each framework. When the request frequency drops from 100 Hz to 0.5 Hz, power consumption values converge toward the system's baseline. However, heavy frameworks exhibit a persistent Static Power Overhead that prevents them from reaching the minimalist baseline established by the micro-frameworks.

The data confirms that minimalist architectures maintain a lower energy profile even in near-idle states. By analysing the median, we observe that Sinatra and F3 establish the lower bound of efficiency. In contrast, even at this sparse request rate, the richer abstraction layers Rails and Laravel result in a persistent energy penalty. In the Python ecosystem, however, the high runtime energy footprint of the interpreter effectively masks the architectural differences between Flask and Django, whereas Fastify seems to be confirmed to be less energy efficient than Express.js.

TAG	COUNT	MIN	AVG	MEDIAN	MAX
F3	324	2.436639	2.866419	2.863427	3.113151
Laravel	324	2.436395	2.906383	2.897789	4.194996
Sinatra	324	2.445612	2.859034	2.854424	3.105339
Ruby on Rails	322	2.456109	3.016800	2.864190	7.397930
Flask	324	2.453363	2.862290	2.858880	3.076408
Django	324	2.420282	2.862931	2.858117	3.065544
Fastify	324	2.447625	2.947286	2.942559	3.162772
Express.js	324	2.451776	2.908441	2.899437	3.220024

Table 5: Summary of the 120-second window test with 1 request every 2s

The Overhead Relative to Baseline: SAPO, SMPO, and SCPJ

By using the historical hardware baseline of 2.8487W (established in ADRN-2) and comparing it against the 120-second low-load dataset, we can quantify the framework-induced power overhead. This study introduces three metrics:

- *Software Average Power Overhead (SAPO)*: Derived from the average, representing the total operational energy cost, including periodic runtime maintenance.

$$SAPO = \frac{(P_{average} - 2.8487)}{2.8487} \times 100$$

- *Software Median Power Overhead (SMPO)*: Derived from the median, it measures the Accidental Complexity defined in ADRN-1. It tells a developer how the sole framework impacts on the power.

$$SMPO = \frac{(P_{median} - 2.8487)}{2.8487} \times 100$$

- *Software Complexity Power Jitter (SCPJ)*: Defined as the absolute value of the delta between Software Average Power Overhead and Software Median Power Overhead (SAPO – SMPO), representing intermittent or bursty runtime activity.

$$SCPJ = |SAPO - SMPO|$$

In the low-load scenario (Table 6), the maximum observed differential between frameworks corresponds to only a few milliwatts, indicating that under very low request rates, the platform's idle (static) power dominates overall consumption.

Framework	SAPO (Average-based)	SCPO (Median-based)	SCPJ
F3	0.62%	0.52%	0.10%
Laravel	2.02%	1.72%	0.30%
Sinatra	0.36%	0.20%	0.16%
Ruby on Rails	5.90%	0.54%	5.36%
Flask	0.48%	0.36%	0.12%
Django	0.50%	0.33%	0.17%
Fastify	3.46%	3.29%	0.16%
Express.js	2.10%	1.78%	0.32%

Table 6: Comparison of SAPO, SCPO, and SCPJ of the 120-second window test with 1 request every 2s (to 2 d.p.).

However, when the workload intensity increases to 100 Hz (Table 7), the architectural overhead scales, with SMPO reaching as high as 76.3860% in complex frameworks. These results demonstrate that framework-induced energy effects become the primary determinant of consumption under sustained workload intensity, whereas under sparse activity, the effects are largely masked by the hardware baseline.

Framework	SAPO (Average-based)	SMPO (Median-based)	SCPJ (Jitter)
F3	41.75%	42.18%	0.43%
Laravel	76.17%	76.39%	0.22%
Sinatra	33.48%	34.66%	1.18%
Ruby on Rails	43.25%	39.37%	3.88%
Flask	43.53%	44.13%	0.60%
Django	45.71%	46.05%	0.35%
Fastify	50.84%	51.29%	0.46%
Express.js	48.61%	48.85%	0.24%

Table 7: Comparison of SAPO, SCPO, and SCPJ of the 120-second window test with 1 request every 0.01s (to 2 d.p.).

Second, despite the small absolute differences, directional relative variation across frameworks is observable. During sparse request handling, lightweight frameworks such as Sinatra, Flask, and F3 introduce less than 1% (Table 6) additional power draw on average, suggesting minimal runtime overhead. In contrast, frameworks with richer abstraction layers (Laravel, Express, Fastify, and Ruby on Rails) exhibit progressively higher overhead. An exception is Django; as previously

reported, it appears that Python's web stack energy footprint is relatively high, which may mask the framework's internal overhead.

Third, these findings highlight an important systemic property of always-on servers: idle power dominates energy behaviour under low workload intensity. Consequently, architectural differences between frameworks become more relevant as workload intensity increases, while under near-idle conditions, the hardware baseline largely masks software-induced effects.

Finally, examining the Software Complexity Power Jitter (SCPJ) reveals a behavioural distinction between framework architectures. As visible in Figure 19 and Figure 20, frameworks with a high delta between average and median overhead introduce intermittent bursts of incidental runtime activity. In the case of Ruby on Rails, transients can peak above 7 W, likely reflecting the complexity of its runtime. In contrast, lightweight frameworks such as Sinatra maintain a near-flat power profile with low SCPJ, indicating minimal bursty or accidental complexity-induced energy overhead.

Figure 19: Sinatra 120-second window - 1 request every 2.00s

Figure 20: Ruby on Rails 120-second window - 1 request every 2.00s

Conclusions

This study confirms that software complexity significantly affects energy efficiency. Lightweight frameworks minimize instantaneous power and establish a lower energy baseline, while more complex frameworks impose a persistent energy overhead that, although small on a per-server basis, can scale to substantial costs across many instances.

While the current investigation focuses on CPU energy draw via Intel RAPL telemetry, an important avenue for future work is the evaluation of memory usage and caching mechanisms. Many frameworks rely on in-memory caching and runtime optimizations to improve throughput, which can have a non-trivial impact on energy consumption. Profiling both CPU and memory footprints would provide a more holistic view of the true energy cost of software complexity, particularly in production scenarios where caching and background processes play a significant role. This would also allow deeper investigation of cases like the JavaScript ecosystem, where performance-oriented frameworks such as Fastify can exhibit higher energy consumption than expected, showing that advertised efficiency does not always translate directly to lower power usage.

Examining Software Complexity Power Jitter (SCPJ) further highlights behavioural differences between frameworks. Lightweight frameworks maintain low SCPJ, indicating minimal bursty or incidental power spikes, whereas complex frameworks can produce intermittent transients, reflecting bursts of runtime activity and higher accidental complexity-induced energy overhead.

In conclusion, software complexity is a primary determinant of the environmental impact of computing. Minimalist frameworks reduce energy consumption and maintain a lower baseline power, whereas feature-rich frameworks increase energy use through both sustained overhead and the bursty activity captured by SCPJ. These results demonstrate that Software Median Power Overhead (SMPO) and SCPJ may serve as effective metrics for quantifying the environmental impact of software, enabling sustainability to be assessed as an objective technical constraint alongside performance and functionality.

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Software And Data Availability

The complete source code, automation scripts, and raw log files used in this project are openly available and permanently archived at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18649446>

AI Usage Statement

This research made limited use of an AI language model to assist in drafting baseline scripts. The AI did not make autonomous decisions, and all outputs were critically reviewed, edited, and approved by the author prior to use.